

SYNTHESIS OF ADSORBENT FROM CITRUS LIMON LEAVES FOR REMOVAL OF HEAVY METALS

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ABSTRACT :

This research focuses on the production of low cost and sustainable type adsorbent production from citrus limon leaves (Lemon) as a raw material. The contamination of water bodies by heavy metals poses a significant threat to environmental and human health. Heavy metal pollution in water systems is a critical environmental issue, necessitating the development of cost-effective and sustainable remediation methods. This study focuses on the synthesis of a bio-based adsorbent from citrus leaves (Citrus limon) for the efficient removal of heavy metals such as lead (Pb^{2+}) from aqueous solutions. This project focuses on the synthesis of an eco-friendly adsorbent using citrus leaves for the efficient removal of heavy metals from aqueous solutions. The preparation of the adsorbent involved several critical steps, including cleaning, drying, grinding, activation, and calcination. Chemical activation was performed using sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4) at varying concentrations to enhance the surface properties, followed by calcination at different temperatures to optimize porosity and surface area. Parameters such as pH, contact time, adsorbent dosage and temperature were systematically studied to evaluate their effect on adsorption efficiency. Characterization of the prepared adsorbent was carried out using techniques such as FTIR, SEM, XRD analysis to understand surface morphology, functional groups. The results demonstrated that citrus leaf-derived adsorbents, especially after optimized activation and calcination, exhibited high adsorption capacities for selected heavy metals such as lead (Pb^{2+}). This study highlights the potential of using low-cost, biodegradable materials for sustainable water purification applications.

INTRODUCTION :

Water pollution caused by the discharge of heavy metals into natural water bodies has become a major environmental and public health concern worldwide. Heavy metals such as lead (Pb^{2+}), cadmium (Cd^{2+}), and chromium (Cr^{6+}) are non-biodegradable, toxic even at low concentrations, and tend to bio-accumulate through the food chain, causing severe health hazards including neurological disorders, kidney damage, and carcinogenesis. Conventional methods for heavy metal removal, such as chemical precipitation, ion exchange, membrane filtration, and electrochemical treatment, often suffer from drawbacks like high operational costs, generation of toxic sludge, and limited applicability to a wide range of metal ions. In recent years, adsorption has emerged as a highly effective, economical, and eco-friendly method for the removal of heavy metals from contaminated water. Particularly, the use of bio-based adsorbents derived from agricultural waste and natural biomass has gained significant attention due to their renew-ability, low cost, and environmental compatibility. Among various plant-based materials, citrus leaves (from species such as Citrus limon) represent an abundant and underutilized biomass resource, rich in cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin, and various functional groups capable of binding heavy metal ions. This study explores the synthesis of an efficient adsorbent using citrus leaves through chemical activation and thermal pyrolysis processes for heavy metals removal here particularly lead. Chemical activation using agents such as sulfuric acid helps in the development of a highly porous structure and the introduction of active surface functional groups. The pyrolysis process, carried out at controlled high

temperatures, further enhances the surface area and pore structure, crucial for effective adsorption. The primary objective of this project is to optimize the activation and pyrolysis parameters to maximize the adsorbent's removal efficiency for various heavy metals. Characterization of the adsorbent using FTIR, SEM, XRD helps to establish a strong correlation between surface properties and adsorption capacity. The findings from this work aim to promote the utilization of citrus waste for sustainable water purification technologies, offering a cost-effective, eco-friendly alternative to traditional heavy metal removal methods, while contributing to waste valorization and circular economy initiatives. Citrus leaves are an abundant and underutilized agricultural byproduct that offer significant potential for use as low-cost adsorbents in water treatment applications. Their natural structure allows for easy chemical modification and thermal treatment, enhancing surface area, porosity, and adsorption efficiency.

MATERIALS AND METHODS :

For a project focused on the synthesis of adsorbent from CLL (Citrus Limon Leaves) , a detailed plan of materials and methods is essential for guiding the experimental process. This section outlines the primary materials required and the methods to be employed, providing a foundation for conducting research in systematic manner and to discuss about the raw materials to be used in the process for the synthesis of the adsorbent from CLL as the project final product to be produced. The methodology involves the processes like preparation of bio-char, pyrolysis & activation, purification, wastewater treatment, adsorbent preparation, neutralization and refining process.

PROCESS SETUP AND FLOW SHEET :

The research was conducted to produce sustainable adsorbent from lemon leaves which involves several process to produce the adsorbent such as washing the raw material using hot water to remove the external contaminates like dust & microbes then it's left under sunlight for several days to dry up and ready for grinding process using pulverizer to produce a fine powder which is known as the bio-mass then it's activated by sulfuric acid and the pyrolysis process done using the muffle furnace which further produces bio-char then the product is neutralized by distilled water for several times and then refined as a adsorbent which is the final product of the research.

The flowsheet for the research is given as per the order of the methodology of the process to produce the adsorbent from lemon leaves.

RESULT & DISCUSSION :

FTIR (FOURIER TRANSFORM INFRARED SPECTROSCOPY)

FTIR GRAPH

Identifies functional groups and chemical bonds in a material. Measures absorption of infrared light at different wavelengths. Useful for detecting surface modifications, organic compounds, and adsorbed species on adsorbents. This helps to understand how adsorbents interact with pollutants or other molecules, by analyzing the shifts or new peaks in the FTIR spectra before and after adsorption, researchers can determine which specific functional groups are responsible for binding

FTIR Analysis Before Activation (Bio-mass)

FTIR Analysis After Activation(Bio-char)

FTIR GRAPH ANALYSIS

PEAK cm ⁻¹	PEAK NAME	FUNCTIONAL GROUP
3429.14	O–H or N–H stretch	Alcohol / Phenol
2925.06	C-H strech	Alkanes
2856.34	C-H strech	Alkanes
1612.01	C=C or C=O strech	Ketones / Aldehydes
1384.22	C-H bending	Methyl
155.48	C-O strech	Ethers
869.78	C-H bending	Aromatics
470.59	Skeletal vibrations	Halides

The broad O–H peak suggests the presence of hydroxyl groups common in bio-based adsorbents and hydrated materials. Peaks around 2925 and 2856 cm⁻¹ indicate aliphatic C–H groups.

The C=C peak at 1612 cm^{-1} suggests the presence of aromatic structures, often associated with carbon-rich or activated materials. Peaks below 1000 cm^{-1} may indicate inorganic components or structural features like silicates or metal oxides.

Each peak in the spectrum corresponds to a specific vibrational mode and the amount of infrared light absorbed at that particular frequency. The location and intensity of peaks provide information about the types of chemical bonds and functional groups present in the sample which is being provided for the test. The intensity of peak can also be related to the concentration of the functional group allowing for quantitative analysis.

XRD GRAPH

XRD (X-Ray Diffraction)

Determines crystalline structure and phase composition of materials. Uses X-rays diffracted by crystal planes to identify atomic arrangements. Useful for distinguishing amorphous vs. crystalline phases in adsorbents. It is a non-destructive technique used to analyze the crystalline structure of materials, it works by shining X-rays on a sample and measuring the angles and intensities of the diffracted X-rays. This data reveals information about the crystal structure, phase composition and orientation of the materials. X-rays with wavelengths comparable to the spacing between atoms in a crystal lattice are directed at the sample, a detector measures the intensity and angles of the diffracted X-rays, creating a diffraction pattern.

Measurement Conditions: (For XRD)

Dataset Name	SS
File name	F:\22.03.1\VINCENT-8\SS.raw
Comment	Scan Mode: Continuous scan mode Scan Type: Locked Coupled Goniometer Stage: Phi Goniometer Control: Diffractometer Controller only Sample Changer: Unknown Sample Changer Measurement Flag: Already measured Sync. Axis: Unknown Sync Axis Beam Optics: Unknown Beam Optics Flag Monochromator: Unknown Monochromator Analyzer: Unknown Analyzer
Measurement Date / Time	3/22/2025 12:41:23 PM
Raw Data Origin	BRUKER-binary V4 (.RAW)
Scan Axis	Gonio
Start Position [°2Th.]	10.0000
End Position [°2Th.]	80.0000
Step Size [°2Th.]	0.0400
Scan Step Time [s]	13.4400
Scan Type	Pre-set time
Offset [°2Th.]	0.0000
Divergence Slit Type	Fixed
Divergence Slit Size [°]	9999.0000
Specimen Length [mm]	10.00
Receiving Slit Size [mm]	0.1000
Measurement Temperature [°C]	25.00
Anode Material	Cu
K-Alpha1 [Å]	1.54060
K-Alpha2 [Å]	1.54443
K-Beta [Å]	1.39225
K-A2 / K-A1 Ratio	0.50000
Generator Settings	30 mA, 40 kV
Diffractometer Type	Theta/Theta
Diffractometer Number	0
Goniometer Radius [mm]	240.00
Dist. Focus-Diverg. Slit [mm]	91.00
Incident Beam Monochromator	No
Spinning	No

The XRD pattern displays a broad peak, indicating amorphous or poorly crystalline structure. The broad full width at half maximum (FWHM) supports this, typical of activated carbons or amorphous oxides. A single dominant peak suggests minimal crystalline phases or high dispersion of crystalline domains in the XRD pattern provided in the graph with the sample as the produced adsorbent from CLL.

The position of a peak in the XRD pattern corresponds to the distance between the atomic planes in the crystal structure. The intensity of a peak is related to the structure factor, which depends on the arrangement of atoms within the unit cell. The shape of a peak provides information about crystalline size and the presence of defects or strain in the material, the width of a peak, of ten measured as the full width at half maximum (FWHM) can be used to estimate crystalline size.

SEM TEST

SEM test typically refers to Scanning Electron Microscopy a technique used to analyze the surface of solid specimens. It involves using a focused beam of electrons to scan the sample's surface and collect signals which then form a high-resolution image, this image reveals information about the sample's topography, composition and other properties.

SEM is widely used in various fields, including materials science, biology, geology, and forensics for tasks such as failure analysis, characterization of materials and defect analysis. Depending on the sample and the analysis goals, sample preparation might be necessary, including coating with a conductive material (e.g., gold) or using low vacuum or low kV imaging to minimize charging and beam damage.

SEM TEST ANALYSIS

1. Surface morphology observations

- The microstructure displays a highly porous and irregular surface topology.
- Pores are of various sizes, with both macro-pores (~10–20 μm) and micro-pores (<5 μm) distributed unevenly across the surface.
- The pore walls are rough, fractured, and sharp-edged, indicating brittle fracture behavior or high mechanical stress history.
- Several voids and channels are interconnected, suggesting a high surface area material, typical of spongy or foamed structures.

2. Texture and Feature

- Layered regions can be observed in certain areas, indicating possible lamellar formation during synthesis or processing.
- Sharp and torn edges around pore openings suggest mechanical breakage rather than slow degradation.

· Some regions show small particle deposition and fine particulates, which could be residue from incomplete reactions or external contamination.

CONCLUSION :

The adsorbent synthesized from *Citrus limon* leaves exhibited promising characteristics for environmental and industrial applications. SEM analysis revealed a highly porous and rough surface morphology, which is essential for effective adsorption processes. The FTIR analysis confirmed the presence of functional groups such as hydroxyl, carbonyl, and aliphatic groups, suggesting a strong potential for interaction with various pollutants.

Overall, *Citrus limon* leaf-derived adsorbent represents a sustainable, eco-friendly, and cost-effective alternative for wastewater treatment, dye removal, and other environmental remediation processes. Further studies on adsorption kinetics, isotherms, and regeneration capabilities are recommended to optimize and scale up its application in real-world systems.

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